

ISic1275

I.Sicily inscription 1275

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140764

1. Περσεφόνη
2. βασιλις ²⁷βασίλισ[σα]?²⁷
3. Κατανα [ίων]
- 4.

Edition: PHI331811

1. Περσεφόνη
2. Βασιλις
3. κατ' [ῶ]να[ρ].
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492881
EDCS 39101644
PHI 140764
PHI 331811

Bibliography

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